

IS ENES3 Data Request Review 2nd July

2nd July, 4pm UK

To join by zoom:- <https://ukri.zoom.us/j/91321680336>

Joined: Mich, Karl, Bryan, Martin, Klaus, Alison, Matt

Apologies: Paul (conflicting meeting)

Context

- Previous Meeting ([20th May, 2020](#)); also <https://zenodo.org/record/3901310>
- CMIP Data Request Roadmap ([Working document](#));
- Reference documents ([google sheet](#)).

Agenda

1. Overview of roadmap .. structure and management of document;
 - need to think about longer term ... getting C3S involved in delivery (Copernicus Climate Change Service).
2. What are the key reusable resources?
 - Physical Variables, e.g. tas, tasmin, ...
 - CMOR grids, e.g. plev8,
 - CMOR Variables, e.g. CMIP6.Amon.tas: monthly mean near surface field -- but note that CMIP6 implementation is not exactly the same as CMIP5.Amon.tas.
 - "structures", e.g. Amon.uas and Amon.vas use the same "structure" specification -- but note the specification and implementation of "structure" in the CMIP5 data request is opaque.
 - There was a discussion of re-usable grid specifications from models, and the need to make them recognisable.

Additional Discussion Notes

Klaus:

--- redefinition of tables in CORDEX ...

--- horizontal grids ... CMIP has standardised records for vertical grids ..

--- registry of horizontal grids

Karl: can get information from the file

Klaus: yes, in principle, but you need to do it Some grids may be functionally equivalent but have differences in floating point numbers.

Bryan, Matt: there are complexities in the details ... but it could still be worthwhile

Matt: if we have a registry .. it could help with ocean data ...

Bryan: we will need to deal with unstructured grids

Bryan: want to publish grids (with DOI)

Karl: weights for regridding WIP has been advocating this for a while.

Martin: modelling centres might want to provide their own .. but we can get started.

Martin: can support through C3S .. Bryan: or CF (Sadie and David).

3. Dealing with priorities:

- Far too many priority=1 requests in CMIP6 (1207 variables, 60% of request -- at June 19, the median [over models] number of priority 1 variables provided is 225, just under 20%);
- WGCM 2019 endorsed concept of enhanced requirements for specification of priority 1 variables, including information on credible ranges and samples from models (this would, intentionally, make it difficult to put a variable at priority 1 if it has not been requested as part of a previous CMIP exercise at a lower priority and been provided by a reasonable range of models);
- Implementation:
 - EU Copernicus project (C3S 34g) is reviewing WGI priority variables (~250 variables, 12% of the CMIP6 requested variables) and can provide a baseline for the enhanced description for new top priority variables.
 - Draft specification for the priority data type:
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1B6bVbGoNDWZmZhvDvfMaws5eUJuouYCDYdEnfpatVAo/edit#>

Matthew: or look at number of MIPs who are interested ...

Bryan: yes ... need to look at combination across MIPs

Klaus: points system ... every MIP gets 100 points

Karl: there is some refinement in request ...

Bryan , Matt: (there is the WG1 list ... should focus on shorter list representative of WG2 needs).

Klaus: essential vs. non-essential.

Martin: currently MIPs assign priority per experiment and variable.

Karl: want to evaluate models ... e.g. ESMVal list ...

Bryan: objective of supporting evaluation is important DECK, as a MIP, should say what they need.

Martin: there is a gap .. no GMD paper requesting data from DECK

Bryan: shout about the gap ... it is right for this group to raise attention to this.

Next WGCM ??

Mich: current plan is to hold a session during Dec. AGU (WGCM plus CMIP).

4. Better management of imports (from CVs, ES-DOC and CF);

- Clarity around dependencies: [review of use cases in roadmap](#).
- Clarity in the schema by following [ISO 19119 and using Data Types](#) : e.g. the value of an 'experiment' attribute in the Data Request would be an instance of an 'CMIPExperiment' Data Type, and the Data Type specification would include details of the import mechanism in a well structured form.

CVs close to data request.

Karl; partly practicality serve ESGF, ES-DOC, Data request, CMOR

Matt: CVs change very frequently